

Studies on Dithiocarbamates. Part IV: Azorhodanines as Acid-Base Indicator

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Although a large number of rhodanyl derivatives are known^{1,2}, to our knowledge, use of rhodanine derivatives as acid-base indicators have not yet been reported. In continuation of our recently reported³ observation on 3-aryl-5-phenylazorhodanines (I), we examined the scope of using azorhodanines as acid-base indicators.

(I)

To this end, pK values of several azorhodanines (see Table I) were spectrophotometrically determined with the help of the following equation⁴,

$$\text{pH} + \log K = \log \frac{D - D_1}{D_1 - D}$$

where D , D_1 and D_2 are observed optical densities in buffer, acid and alkali media respectively. Since dilute solutions have been used, the influence of ionic strength (μ) has been ignored.

In alcoholic solutions, the azo-derivatives are known³ to exhibit λ_{max} around 420 $m\mu$ in the visible region and the absorption characteristics with different buffers indicated isobestic points on both sides of λ_{max} . Hence optical densities were measured at wavelengths close to λ_{max} but well away from the isobestic points (450 $m\mu$ for No. 8 and 430 $m\mu$ for the rest). Further, to avoid troubles arising from precipitation in aqueous medium, buffers containing 40% (by volume) ethanol were used during this work. Pertinent data on our findings are shown in Table I.

Salient points of these observations are: (a) pK values of 3-aryl-5-phenylazorhodanines are very close to each other but 3-alkyl-5-phenylazorhodanines tend to show higher pK

1. Brown, *Chem. Revs.*, 1961, 41, 463.

2. Talukdar, *Ind. J. Appl. Chem.*, 1965, 28, 197.

3. Talukdar and Sengupta, *This Journal*.

4. Wilson, Newcombe, Denaro, Rickett, "Experiments in Physical Chemistry", Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1962, p. 102.

values. However, the presence of a polar group in phenyl-azo moiety can significantly alter these values (nos. 7 & 8, Table I).

TABLE I
Characteristic constants of Azorhodanines

No.	Compound (I) ^a R	R'	pK	Isobestic Point (m μ)	Reported ⁵ EtOH $\lambda_{\max}$ (m μ)
1.	Cyclohexyl	H	8.00	375, 460	422
2.	Benzyl	H	7.60	374, 459	424
3.	Phenyl	H	7.60	375, 460	420
4.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	7.30	377, 455	422
5.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	H	7.50	373, 460	422
6.	<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	H	7.55	376, 455	420
7.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -OEt.	7.25	3.88, 462	446
8.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	6.65	487	424

(a) Satisfactory analysis were obtained for all these compounds.

(b) The deep yellow colour in acidic medium usually changes to a pink colour on the alkaline side. In presence or absence of a buffer, the pink colour, in general, slowly disappears after several hours (4-5). This is presumably due to fission of the rhodanine ring by alkali. However, the pink colour of the *p*-nitro derivative (no. 8) was rapidly discharged in absence of a buffer.

(c) In the usual acid-alkali titrations, 3-4 drops of 0.01% w/v ethanolic solutions gave sharp end points and the results were identical when compared with standard indicators⁵ of known pK values, e.g. bromothymol blue (pK 7.0), phenol red (pK 7.9), phenolphthalein (pK 9.6).

(d) Among the commonly used indicators⁵, there is hardly any indicator with pK value around 7.5; to this extent, the above indicators might prove to be useful in some cases.

Procedure for pK determination—Buffers were prepared at 0.5 unit interval over the pH range 5-10, and in all cases 'Analar' grade chemicals were used. Citrate and phosphate buffers were used in the acid region and borate buffer in the alkaline region. pH of the buffers were checked with Cambridge pH meter, model no. L 378877. Optical densities were obtained with Hilger Uvispek in 1 c.m. matched quartz cells. All measurements were done in duplicate at 25 $\pm$ 0.5°.

Stock solutions of the azo-compounds (I) were prepared in 95% ethanol. Aliquots of these solutions were diluted with appropriate buffer and the final concentrations of the indicators were in the order of 10-15 γ /ml. and Beer's Law was found to hold good for all the compounds around this concentration.

5. Vogel, A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis, Longmans, Green and Co., London, 1959 impress.

pK Values were graphically derived from the intercept on the pH -axis of the linear plot of pH vs. $\log (D-D_1)/(D_s-D_1)$; maximum error for the estimated pK values is ± 0.05 unit.

Our sincere thanks are due to Mr. P. Bagchi, Research Director, for his keen interest in these investigations.

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Received June 30, 1968.